

Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Related Substances in Selpercatinib Bulk Dosage Form By RP-HPLC Technique

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to develop and validate a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for the quantification of related substances (Impurities A and B) in Selpercatinib. The optimized chromatographic conditions included the use of a gradient mode HPLC/PDA system with an Inertsil C18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm), and mobile phase consisting of NaH₂PO₄ at pH 4 with methanol. The flow rate was set at 1.0 mL/min, with detection at 238 nm. The method was evaluated based on linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, and degradation studies. Linearity assessments showed strong correlation coefficients ($r^2 > 0.999$) within the tested concentration ranges, while precision experiments demonstrated minimal variation with %RSD values below 2, ensuring method reliability. Accuracy tests indicated excellent recovery rates between 98–102% for Selpercatinib & 90–110% for Impurities A & B, supporting the effectiveness of the method in quantifying selpercatinib and its impurities. The degradation studies provided insights into stability, ensuring method applicability for routine quality control and stability testing. These optimized chromatographic conditions establish a reliable analytical approach for maintaining drug purity and regulatory compliance in pharmaceutical development.

Keywords: Selpercatinib, related substances, RPHLC, degradation studies, method development and validation.

INTRODUCTION

Bulk Pharmaceutical chemicals or API: "A substance used in finished pharmaceutical product (FPP), intended to furnish pharmacological activity or to otherwise have direct effect in the diagnosis, cure, mitigation, treatment, or prevention of disease, or to have direct effect in restoring, correcting, or modifying physiological functions in human beings," is the definition of an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) according to the World Health Organization. Bulk pharmaceutical chemicals and drug compounds are other words that are frequently used to refer to APIs. [1, 2] RET mutations are found in about 20–30% of sporadic forms of papillary thyroid carcinoma, 70% of the medullary variant of thyroid cancer, and 1–2% of non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC). [3, 4]

The powder form of selpercatinib ranges from white to light yellow and has a modest hygroscopicity. Selpercatinib's water solubility varies with pH, becoming nearly insoluble at neutral pH and sparingly soluble at low pH. [5] Selpercatinib's molecular weight is 525.61 g/mol, and its chemical formula is C₂₉H₃₁N₇O₃. Edema, diarrhoea, exhaustion, dry mouth, hypertension, abdominal pain, constipation, rash, nausea, and headache were the most frequent side effects (≥25%). [6] Selpercatinib is believed to have a better safety profile than other multi-kinase inhibitors because of its higher specificity for RET over other tyrosine kinases. [7] Selpercatinib competes with ATP for binding, hence directly inhibiting RET auto phosphorylation. [8] Two major oncogenic activators of RET are known to be chromosomal rearrangement and gene mutations. [9]

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Because it may be used to analyze pharmaceuticals that are mildly polar or apolar, RP-HPLC, which is currently the gold standard for PDA, is still a favoured technology. Since impurities eventually impact the safety of the drug when used, the pharmaceutical industry and regulatory bodies have become very concerned with their separation, identification, isolation, evaluation, and management. Related substances are structurally related to a drug substance. These substances may be (a) identified or unidentified impurities arising from the synthesis manufacturing process, such as starting materials, intermediates, or by-products, and do not increase on storage, or (b) identified or unidentified degradation products that result from drug substance or drug product manufacturing processes or arise during storage of a material. Related substances are classified either as Degradation Related Impurities (DPI) or rarely as Process Related Impurities (PRI).^[10, 11]

Importance of Related Substances Determination:

To ensure the efficacy, safety, and quality of pharmaceutical products, related substances in drug substances and pharmaceutical formulations must be identified. If present in excess of permissible limits, related substances which might result from degradation, production methods, or starting materials can be harmful or impair the effectiveness of drugs. Manufacturers can guarantee batch-to-batch

uniformity, control medicine purity, and set up suitable storage conditions and shelf life by detecting and measuring these contaminants. Additionally, impurity profiling aids in comprehending and refining the production process to reduce the generation of impurities. To ensure adherence to international quality standards, regulatory guidelines like ICH Q3A and Q6A mandate the identification and qualification of contaminants. Therefore, the determination of related substances is a critical part of quality assurance, ensuring that the final pharmaceutical product is safe, stable, and effective for patient use. 1–2 methods were reported for quantitative determination of related substances in selpercatinib using the HPLC method.^[12,13] In order to identify and estimate associated compounds (impurity-A and impurity-B) in Selpercatinib Bulk Dosage Form, this work sought to develop a RP-HPLC method. The objectives of the study are: to develop accurate and robust RP-HPLC method, to validate the method as per ICH Q2 series guidelines, to develop an efficient method with improved separation and reduced retention time and to optimize the analytical conditions in order to achieve good resolution and tailing factor, to evaluate the stability of the selpercatinib under various conditions & to apply the validated method to real pharmaceutical samples for routine quality control and stability testing.

Fig 1: Structure of selpercatinib

Fig 2: Structure of Impurity-A & Impurity-B

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD:

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents:

Selpercatinib was procured from Indian Pharma. Impurity-A (selpercatinib amide) and Impurity-B (selpercatinib Metabolite, M2) were sourced from Simson Pharma Ltd, Mumbai, India. HPLC grade Milli-Q water and methanol, and HCl, Hydrogen peroxide and NaOH were obtained from Merck, Mumbai, India and HPLC grade acetonitrile was sourced from Molychem, Hyderabad, India. KH_2PO_4 was sourced from Finer chemical limited and NaH_2PO_4 was sourced from Qualigens, Mumbai, India.

2.2. Instrument:

This study utilized Waters HPLC equipped with PDA detector (Waters 996) and EMPOWER 3 software.

2.3. Preparation of Solutions:

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer:

Accurately weighed 6.4 g of Sodium di-hydrogen orthophosphate is transferred to 1000 mL volumetric flask. Add about 800 mL of HPLC water and dissolve by stirring. Measure the pH using calibrated pH meter and adjust the pH to 4.0 by slowly adding 1N NaOH with continuous stirring. After reaching pH 4.0, make up the volume to 1000 ml with HPLC water. Mix thoroughly to ensure a homogeneous buffer solution. Filter through a 0.45 μm membrane filter and sonicate it for 10 min.

Diluent: Methanol is used as diluent.

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solution for Selpercatinib Bulk Drug:

Selpercatinib Standard Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of pure selpercatinib into a 10 mL clean dry volumetric flask. Add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the diluent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 1 mL of the above stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent (working standard) and finally filter the

working standard solution through a 0.45 μm syringe filter.

Impurities A and B Standard Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 1 mg of Impurity-A and 1mg of Impurity-B into a 10 mL clean dry volumetric flask each. Add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the diluent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1 mL of the above stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent (working standard) and finally filter the working standard solution through a 0.45 μm syringe filter.

Test solution preparation:

Accurately weigh an amount of selpercatinib equivalent to 10 mg API from the bulk material and transfer it into a 10 mL clean dry volumetric flask. Add diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the diluent. (Stock solution)

Prepare the working sample by diluting an appropriate volume of stock solution to match the standard concentration and finally filter the working sample solution through a 0.45 μm syringe filter.

Mixed solution preparation:

In a 10 mL volumetric flask combine appropriate volumes of standard selpercatinib solution 1 mL of 1000 ppm and Impurity standard solutions 0.1ml of each 100 ppm impurity. Adjust the volume to 10 mL with diluent. Pass the mixed solution through a 0.45 μm membrane filter.

Inject 10–20 μL of the mixed solution and check for system suitability parameters.

2.4. Method Development:

UV spectrum of dilute solutions of selpercatinib and impurities A and B were recorded by scanning in the range of 190 nm to 400 nm using PDA detector. The detection wavelength is selected and typically set at 238 nm, where selpercatinib and impurities A and B showed sufficient absorbance or absolute maxima. At the beginning of the work, isocratic elution was

attempted to isolate the selpercatinib and its impurities, with various configurations of stationary phases and compositions of mobile phase (methanol, KH_2PO_4 and NaH_2PO_4) with varying pH. However, the chromatograms revealed that the separation of components is ineffective with poor peak shape. Hence, I considered using gradient elution for further investigation. Gradient condition (Mobile phase A - NaH_2PO_4 , pH adjusted to 4 and Mobile phase B - Methanol) which follows the sequence 0 min (10%B), 0–5 min (10%B to 30%B), 5–10 min (30%B), 10–15 min (30%B to 50%B), 15–20 min (50%B to 10%B), 20–25 min (10%B) is selected as optimized condition as the chromatogram revealed Good peak shape, resolution between selpercatinib and impurities A and B was found to be 5.91 and 6.12, and Tailing factor not more than 1.5 meeting the detection standards.

2.5. Method Validation: The developed method was validated to ensure its suitability for analyzing related substances in Selpercatinib as per ICH guidelines and literature. Parameters such as specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, range, LOD and LOQ, robustness and range were evaluated.

2.5.1. **Specificity:** The specificity of the method was performed by injecting blank sample to demonstrate the absence of interference with the elution of selpercatinib and Impurities A and B.

2.5.2. **Linearity:** The stock solutions of selpercatinib and Impurities A and B were diluted to produce concentrations in the range of 10–50 ppm for selpercatinib and 1–5 ppm for Impurities A and B. The Linearity was determined from regression coefficients.

2.5.3. **Precision:** Precision of the method was evaluated by injecting 6 homogeneous mixture of selpercatinib and Impurities A & B mixed solution at target concentration (middle concentration in Linearity). The %RSD of areas was determined and if it is less or equal to 2 was treated as acceptable.

2.5.4. **Accuracy:** Accuracy was determined by performing recovery studies at 3 different concentration levels (50%, 100%, and 150%) in triplicate with reference to target concentration. The % recovery should be within the range of 98-102% for

selpercatinib and 90-110% for impurities A&B was treated as acceptable.

2.5.5. **LOD and LOQ:** The LOD and LOQ of the method were evaluated by measuring the responses at S/N ratio of 3:1 and 10:1 for selpercatinib and Impurities A and B.

2.5.6. **Robustness:** The method robustness was assessed by deliberate changes in analytical parameters (flow rate and mobile phase composition) and if it is met the expected performance criteria then it was treated as acceptable.

2.5.7. **Forced degradation studies:** The stability of the selpercatinib under different conditions such as acid, base, thermal, peroxide and UV were studied and from the chromatograms and chromatographic responses the % degradation is evaluated. % degradation of selpercatinib should not exceed 10%.

In acid degradation, to the freshly prepared target concentration of selpercatinib add 0.1N HCl in 10 mL volumetric flask and kept in darkness for 12 hrs and then refluxed at 60°C for 1hr. The solution is neutralized using 0.1N NaOH and dilute up to calibration mark using methanol.

The base degradation is similar to acid degradation but 0.1N NaOH was used to treat the solution and 0.1N HCl was used to neutralize the solution. In oxidative/peroxide degradation the selpercatinib solution is added with 3% H_2O_2 and kept in darkness for 12 hrs and refluxed at 60°C for 1 hr.

In thermal degradation the selpercatinib solution was kept in an oven at 105°C for 12 hrs.

In photolytic degradation the selpercatinib solution was illuminated with UV for 12 hrs.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Instrument: HPLC equipped with Auto sampler and PDA detector

Mode: Gradient

Column: Inertsil C18, (250*4.6 mm, 5 μm)

Mobile phase: NaH_2PO_4 pH 4 (M.P-A): Methanol (M.P-B)

Flow rate: 1 mL/min

Column Temperature: Ambient

Wavelength: 238 nm

Injection volume: 10 μL

Run time: 25 min

Fig 3: Standard chromatogram of Selpercatinib and Impurities A and B

The system suitability parameters such as N , R_s and A_s should be $N > 2000$, $R_s > 2$ and $A_s < 2$ as per ICH guidelines. System suitability parameters of selpercatinib and Impurities A and B were within the limits. Hence, the method could be used for analyzing related substances in selpercatinib. The specificity of the method was evaluated by comparing the blank chromatogram with optimized chromatogram and observation that there was no interference with the elution of selpercatinib and impurities A and B i.e., absence of interference at R_t of selpercatinib (12.667 min), Impurity A (9.131 min) and Impurity B (14.460 min). Hence, the method is specific.

Fig 4: Blank Chromatogram

Linearity of the method was observed at concentrations 10–50 ppm for selpercatinib and 1–5 ppm for Impurities A and B from the calibration curves (Concentration on X-axis and Peak areas on Y-axis) and the r^2 of selpercatinib and Impurities A and B were within the limits i.e., $r^2 = 0.999$ which demonstrates that the method can quantify the components at lower concentrations

Fig 5: Calibration curve for selpercatinib

Fig 6: Calibration curve for Impurity-A & B

Repeatability and intermediate precision were used to evaluate the method's precision. It was found that the %RSD values were less than two for the peak area responses of six determinations at the target concentration (100% of the sample or middle concentration in linearity), indicating that the method is accurate and suitable for routine component analysis. The method demonstrated good sensitivity, with LOD and LOQ determined based on the signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio. The limits of detection (LOD) for selpercatinib and impurities A and B were found to be 0.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 0.003 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and 0.0029 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. The limits of quantitation (LOQ) for selpercatinib and impurities A and B were 0.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 0.0099 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and 0.009 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively.

Robustness results for variations in flow rate and mobile phase (%B) composition was observed and there were no considerable changes were observed in the system suitability parameters. Forced degradation studies revealed that selpercatinib underwent 1.06%

degradation under acidic conditions, 3.47% in basic conditions, 5.89% in oxidative (peroxide) conditions, 7.06% under thermal stress, and 5.80% upon exposure to UV light.

Table-1: Results of forced degradation studies

Condition	% Degradation of Selpercatinib
Acid	1.06
Base	3.47
Peroxide	5.89
Thermal	7.06
UV light	5.80

Table-2: Summary of results for method validation

S. No	Parameter	Selpercatinib	Impurity-A	Impurity-B
1.	Retention time (min)	12.66	9.13	14.46
2.	Resolution (R_s)	5.91	-	6.12
3.	Tailing Factor	1.11	1.07	1.24
4.	Theoretical Plates(N)	5206	3251	4257
5.	Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	10–50	1–5	1–5
6.	Slope	15065	1468	1229.7
7.	Intercept	952.38	23.905	8.619
8.	Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9993	0.9998	0.9999
9.	Intra-day precision (%RSD) (n=6)	0.7	0.5	0.6
10.	Intermediate precision (%RSD)	0.8	0.5	0.3
11.	Accuracy at 50% level: Average results (n=3)			
	Spiked conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	15	1.5	1.5
	Determined conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	14.99	1.43	1.45
	%Recovery	99.9	95.3	96.6
	Accuracy at 100% level: Average results (n=3)			
	Spiked conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	30	3	3
	Determined conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	29.77	2.98	2.99
	%Recovery	99.2	99.3	99.6
	Accuracy at 150% level: Average results (n=3)			
	Spiked conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	45	4.5	4.5
	Determined conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	44.86	4.48	4.42
	%Recovery	99.6	99.5	98.2
	Mean Recovery	99.5	98.03	98.13
12.	Sensitivity			
	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.01	0.003	0.0029
	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.06	0.0099	0.009

Fig 7: A Chromatogram of the Selpercatinib Bulk Dosage Form showing well resolved & symmetrically shaped peaks corresponding to analytes under study.

4. CONCLUSION:

This study introduces RP-HPLC method for estimating the related substances in Selpercatinib Bulk Dosage Form. The optimized chromatographic conditions included the use of a gradient mode HPLC system with an Inertsil C18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm), and mobile phase consisting of NaH₂PO₄ at pH 4 with Methanol. All regulatory requirements and acceptance criteria were satisfied by the validated analytical method for selpercatinib, guaranteeing accuracy in measuring the medication and associated contaminants. According to the study, the method is suitable for routine quality control and stability testing of selpercatinib because it is linear, sensitive, robust, precise, accurate, and capable of estimating process-related impurities. Studies of deterioration in peroxide, acidic, basic, thermal, and photolytic environments showed different levels of degradation. The drug's stability was demonstrated by the degradation values, which stayed within acceptable bounds. The pharmaceutical industry's ability to maintain drug safety, efficacy, and purity is greatly aided by these findings.

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